

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP1 – Evidence Workflow Development

D1.4 Development of an EHDEN Academy Course on Implementation of RMM Effectiveness Testing Methods

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full meaning
CDM	Common Data Model
DDD	Defined Daily Dose
DUS	Drug Utilisation
ENCePP	European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EHDEN	European Health Data and Evidence Network
EMIF	European Medical Information Framework
EU	European Union
ISPE	International Society of Pharmaco-Epidemiology
mMPR	modified Medication Possession Ratio
PDC	Proportion Days Covered
PDD	Prescribed Daily dose
RRE	Remote Research Environment
RMM	Risk minimisation measure
CPD	Change point detection

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V1	15 February 2022	First Draft
V2	23 February 2022	For Consortium Review
V3	04 March 2022	Submitted to IMI

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	European Patients’ Forum (EPF) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL – Switzerland
BI	Boehringer Ingelheim – Germany

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The EHDEN Academy (academy.ehden.eu) is an online educational resource for anyone working in the domain of real world data and real world evidence. Originating in the European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN) IMI2 project, its goal is to build upon the foundations of that project and its collaboration with the Observational Health Data Science and Informatics (OHDSI). The EHDEN Academy offers a number of courses related to real world data harmonisation and analysis using standardised analytical tools and infrastructure.

In this work a new EHDEN Academy course on “Methods for time series analysis, with application to Risk Minimisation Measures (RMM) Effectiveness Testing” has been developed. RMM are used by regulatory authorities to ensure and improve the safe use of a drug once it has been approved for use. Typical examples of RMM include changes in the conditions of marketing authorisation and/or changes in the conditions of use or label characteristics. Evaluating the impact of such regulatory measures is needed to measure immediate as well as long-term effects on drug uptake and use in the community.

The course covers basics of change point detection theory for examining trends over time and its application to testing the effectiveness of risk minimisation measures. Users learn how to apply change point detection methods using an interactive online tool. The tool enables users to select from a range of time-series change detection methods to a) determine the effect of known interventions/changes, and b) to detect plausible changes, in a data-driven manner. Users can select the time-series, methods, and interventions of interest and view the results of the RMM test in real-time. A demo is included showing the changes over time in the use of drugs for COVID-19 treatment.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In discussion with the EHDEN Academy project team a new course is under development. The course covers basics of time-series change point detection theory and its application to testing the effectiveness of risk minimisation measures (RMM). RMM are used by regulatory authorities to ensure and improve the safe use of a drug once it has been approved for use. Typical examples of RMM include changes in the conditions of marketing authorisation and/or changes in the conditions of use or label characteristics. The RMM effectiveness testing tool was developed as part of EHDEN IMI2 project. Users learn how to apply change point detection methods using an interactive online tool. The tool enables users to apply a range of time-series change detection methods to a) determine the effect of known interventions/changes, and b) to detect plausible changes, in a data-driven manner. Users can select the time-series, methods, and interventions of interest and view the results of the RMM test in real-time. A demo is included showing the changes over time in the use of drug for COVID-19 treatment. The course is suitable for beginners.

2. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The overall aim of this work is to develop an EHDEN Academy training course on the RMM effectiveness testing tool which is designed to aid the study of drug utilisation patterns over time.

3. STORYBOARD

In this section the storyboard for the course is described. The storyboard forms the basis of the course structure and content.

3.1 Introduction Text

Biography

This section will contain brief bios of the two course instructors.

Sara Khalid

Antony Sena

Learning Objectives

In this course you will learn how data-driven techniques can be used to find changes in time-series, with the help of applied examples such as testing the effectiveness of risk minimisation measures.

By the end, you will be able to use the time-series tool to find change points in real-world data.

Prerequisites

EHDEN Academy Courses:

- Phenotype Definition, Characterization & Evaluation

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Pre-reading/References

On change detection theory and related applications

- Bernal J, Cummins S, Gasparrini A. Interrupted time series regression for the evaluation of public health interventions: a tutorial, *International Journal of Epidemiology*, Volume 46, Issue 1, February 2017, Pages 348–355, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw098>
- van den Burg, G and Williams, C. An Evaluation of Change Point Detection Algorithms. *arXiv preprint 2020*; *arXiv:2003.06222*.
- Adams R and MacKay D. Bayesian online changepoint detection. *ArXiv Preprint 2007*. ArXiv:0710.3742.
- Muggeo VM. Estimating regression models with unknown break-points. *Stat Med*. 2003 Oct 15;22(19):3055-71. doi: 10.1002/sim.1545. PMID: 12973787.
- Judge A, Wallace G, Prieto-Alhambra D, Arden N, Edwards C. Can the publication of guidelines change the management of early rheumatoid arthritis? An interrupted time series analysis from the United Kingdom, *Rheumatology*, Volume 54, Issue 12, December 2015, Pages 2244–2248, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rheumatology/kev268>

On data harmonisation

- The Book of OHDSI: Chapter 10 on Defining Cohorts and Chapter 9 on using R. <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/NetworkResearch.html>

On drug utilisation patterns during the COVID-19 pandemic

- Prats-Urbe A, Sena A G, Lai L Y H, Ahmed W, Alghoul H, Alser O et al. Use of repurposed and adjuvant drugs in hospital patients with COVID-19: multinational network cohort study *BMJ* 2021; 373 :n1038 doi:10.1136/bmj.n1038

On risk minimisation measures

- Berencsi K, Sami A, Ali MS, Marinier K, Deltour N, Perez-Gutthann S, Pedersen L, Rijnbeek P, Van der Lei J, Lapi F, Simonetti M, Reyes C, Sturkenboom MCJM, Prieto-Alhambra D. Impact of risk minimisation measures on the use of strontium ranelate in Europe: a multi-national cohort study in 5 EU countries by the EU-ADR Alliance. *Osteoporos Int*. 2020 Apr;31(4):721-755. doi: 10.1007/s00198-019-05181-6. Epub 2019 Nov 6. Erratum in: *Osteoporos Int*. 2020 Feb 5;: PMID: 31696274.

3.2 Chapters

Introduction

1. Basic principles of time series analysis
2. Use of Time Series analysis in risk minimisation measures testing
3. How do we apply this to observational data?

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Applied Examples

The choice of the selected example scenarios included in the course was motivated by a number of factors including data availability, compatibility with OHDSI infrastructure, and continuity with EHDEN Academy courses e.g., a related course on treatment patterns. With these considerations in view, the following examples are designed to illustrate a) the same drug used by two different patient groups over two different time periods, and b) a comparison of two different drugs used by the same patient group over the same time period.

Example 1: Changes over time in use of hydroxychloroquine by rheumatoid arthritis (RA) patients

- **Background:** rheumatoid arthritis (RA) guidelines recommend using Methotrexate as first line therapy from 2008, possibly ‘displacing’ hydroxychloroquine (HCQ), Figure 1.
- **Data:**
 - Initiation of first line HCQ for RA
 - GP prescriptions in THIN (UK)
- **Period:** 2000 – 2018
- **Change Point Detection Results:**

Figure 1. The number of annual HCQ prescriptions in UK (y-axis) over time from the year 2000 to 2018 (x-axis). Left: Segmented linear regression with one change point detected. The initial location of the change point pre-specified by user is indicated by a red circle, along with a horizontal line marking the confidence interval around that change point. Regression lines representing the regression equations fitted to each segment are also shown in green and blue colours. The (data-driven) location of the change point estimated by the model is marked by a vertical dashed line in red on the x-axis. Centre: Segmented linear regression with two initial change points pre-specified by user (red circles). Regression lines representing the regression equations fitted to each of the three segments are shown in green and blue colours. 95%CI around the pre-specified changepoints are shown in horizontal red lines. Finally, the (data-driven) location of a single changepoint estimated by the model is indicated by the vertical dashed line. Right: Bayesian online change point detection, where no location is pre-specified by user, and the method can estimate one or more change points. Here the correct change point is at the year 2009 (the first timepoint shown here as a changepoint was a feature of the original model that has now been corrected in the prototype). The Bayesian method provides a probability of there being a change point for each given time point (not shown here), whereas the segmented regression provides a confidence interval around each estimated change point.

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Example 2: Changes over time in use of hydroxychloroquine by COVID-19 patients

- **Background:**
 - HCQ received emergency approval by FDA in March 2020
 - Regulatory action followed in late April due to cardiovascular safety issues
- **Data:** HCQ for COVID-19 treatment
- **Database:** IQVIA Open Claims (USA)
- **Period:** Jan – Oct 2020
- **Change point detection Results:**

Figure 2. The number of monthly HCQ prescriptions for COVID-19 patients (y-axis) over time from January (month 1) to October 2020 (month 10) (x-axis), available in the IQVIA Open Claims (USA) database. Left: Segmented linear regression. The location of a changepoint is marked by a vertical dashed line in red on the x-axis, along with a horizontal line marking the confidence Interval around the estimated change point. Regression lines representing the regression equations fitted to each segment are also shown. Right: Bayesian online change point detection, with the location of a changepoint marked by a vertical dashed line in red on the x-axis. Note: same data used in both plots; however, the Y-axis of the left plot wider to allow plotting of regression model including error bar in grey. Note: y-axis in final tool will be scaled to 0.

Example 3: Changes over time in use of dexamethasone by COVID-19 patients

- **Background:** RECOVERY RCT report 30% reduction in mortality in late June 2020 with dexamethasone (DXM)
- **Data:** DXM for COVID-19 treatment
- **Databases:** IQVIA Open Claims (USA), IQVIA Hospital Records (USA)
- **Period:** Jan – Oct 2020
- **Change point detection Results:**

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Figure 3. The number of monthly Dexamethasone prescriptions for COVID-19 patients (y-axis) available in the IQVIA Open Claims (USA) database. Top: IQVIA Open Claims (USA), over time from January (month 1) to October 2020 (month 10) (x-axis). Bottom: IQVIA Hospital (USA), over time from January (month 1) to July 2020 (month 7) (x-axis). Left: Segmented linear regression. The location of a changepoint is marked by a vertical dashed line in red on the x-axis, along with a horizontal line marking the confidence Interval around the estimated change point. Regression lines representing the regression equations fitted to each segment are also shown. Right: Bayesian online change point detection, with the location of a changepoint marked by a vertical dashed line in red on the x-axis. Note: y-axis in final tool will be scaled to 0.

Using the Tool

This section will provide step-by-step guidance on how to use the tool to select the population of interest and the analysis settings:

Study Design

1. Defining the population
2. Defining the time frame to study the usage patterns
3. Constructing cohort(s) to model the study populations of interest (see Figure 4 for an example view)

Using the RMM Package and Tool

1. Importing cohorts from ATLAS (will require course pre-requisites)
2. Running the analysis using <https://github.com/EHDEN/TimeSeriesAnalysis>
3. Exploring the output via tool (interactive Shiny app) (see Figure 5 for an example view)

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Figure 4. Cohort Counts in the R Shiny app for the tool: using the drop-down menu on the left, the application provides a summary of cohort counts used in the analysis for each database.

Figure 5. Time-series exploration in the R Shiny app for the tool: participants can visually inspect the results of the various time series analyses using the “Time Series” menu option. The menu items allow the user to filter based on the database(s) of interest, the target and event cohorts, and the time window (covered in course chapters).

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Selecting analysis of choice

Users will be able to set analysis setting from the combinations in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Change point detection methods included in the tool along with the settings that can be selected by the user.

Method	Model	Location	Number of change points	Output
Segmented Regression (reference method)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Linear piece-wise regression ○ Poisson piece-wise regression 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pre-specified ○ Data-driven 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1 ○ 2 ○ Data-driven ○ Fixed (1 changepoint) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Slope and intercept of each segment ○ Estimated change point(s)
Bayesian Online	Bayesian inference	Data-driven	Data-driven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Probability of change at each time point ○ Estimated change point(s)

Summary

Applied the Time Series analysis in this specific use case: talk through how to generalise this using the same tools & framework/approach.

3.3 Course Materials

- Text Description
- Video (with slides)
- Vignette and Paper
- Link to online RMM testing tool
- Quiz/Exam

4. COURSE EVALUATION

The following knowledge trackers will be evaluated:

5. Enrolment figures
6. Quiz/Exam results (% pass)
7. Participant feedback (qualitative)

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5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A new EHDEN Academy course has been proposed. The storyboard for the course has been developed and presented in this report. The course will be offered complementarily to the EHDEN Academy course on Analysis of Treatment Patterns. Both courses are under development and will be available at <https://academy.ehden.eu> in late Spring 2022.